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Research Article

**THE ATTITUDE OF CHILDREN'S TOWARDS THE PRACTICE
OF GLOVES BY DENTISTS**¹Dr Ayesha Shabbir, ²Dr Qurat-ul-ain bukhari, ³Dr Usama Hafeez¹Ex house officer Ibne Sena hospital Multan / Dental Surgeon, ²Ex house officer Ibne Sena hospital Multan, ³House officer Ibne Sena hospital Multan.**Article Received:** July 2020**Accepted:** August 2020**Published:** September 2020**Abstract:**

Aim: The aim of the study was to assess the attitude of parents and their children to the use of gloves by dentists in a dental office. 314 parents and their children attending the pediatric department were asked to participate in the study. Children aged 11-15 took part. A questionnaire was used in the research.

Methods: In the Dental department of Nishtar dental hospital, Multan for one-year duration from March 2019 to March 2020.

Results: The majority of children and their parents (94.9% and 96.2%, respectively) stated that wearing gloves is important during dental treatment. The majority of participants stated that gloves are worn to protect the doctor and patient (94.9% and 90.8%, respectively). 94.4% of children and parents did not like going to the dentist who did not wear gloves. Most of the children 92.3% and parents 94.9% believed that gloves should be changed after each patient's dental treatment.

Conclusion: Most of the participants in this study indicated that dentists should wear gloves when treating their patients and would not bring children to a dentist who did not have adequate infection control procedures. The study found no significant difference in the responses between children and their parents.

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INTRODUCTION:

The increase in the incidence of diseases such as AIDS and hepatitis is leading to the realization of cross infection control measures in dental surgery. So many authorities have developed comprehensive guidelines for infection control in the dental practice. One important recommendation in these guidelines is the routine use of gloves by dentists. Gloves can be worn for a number of reasons, namely to protect the operator from patient-borne infection, to avoid patient-to-patient transmission, and to reassure patients and their parents that the operator is aware of the dangers of cross-contamination, and to take action. to avoid it. The proportion of dentists who routinely use gloves when treating their patients is greater compared to dentists who never wear gloves or use gloves for selected patients or procedures. The dentists listed several reasons for the non-routine use of gloves, such as decreased sensation, limited movement, low risk of infection, patient acceptance, lack of supplies, cost, and more.

Much research has been done to assess the dentist's and adult patients' attitudes towards the use of gloves; however, children's attitudes to the use of gloves by dentists have not been recorded. Therefore, the aim of this study was to investigate children's awareness of the importance of using gloves by dentists and to compare their reactions with their parents.

METHODOLOGY:

A survey was conducted involving children and their parents attending the dental department of Nishtar dental hospital, Multan for one-year duration from March 2019 to March 2020. The questionnaire was to explain the patient's attitude towards the use of gloves by dentists. The questions were; Do you think dentists should wear gloves when treating patients? Are gloves worn to protect dentists or patients? Will you go to a dentist who didn't wear gloves? And do you think dentists should change gloves between patients, or is it enough to wash your hands with gloves? The participants completed questionnaires at the dentist's office after the children had finished their treatment. Oral consent was obtained from parents of children aged 11 to 15. The mean age of the children was 13.4 years with an SD + 2.3.

The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics, and the chi-square test was used to assess the relationship between the parents' and children's responses to the questions, and the significance level was set at 5%.

RESULTS:

300 participants (157 children and 157 parents) took part in the conference. The majority of children and their parents (94.9% and 96.2%, respectively) stated that wearing gloves is important during dental treatment (Table 1).

TABLE 1: RESPONSE OF CHILDREN AND THEIR PARENTS ON WHETHER DENTIST SHOULD WEAR GLOVES WHILE TREATING PATIENTS

	Yes No (%)	No No (%)	Don't know No (%)
Children	149 (94.9%)	3 (2%)	4 (2.5%)
Parents	151 (96.2%)	6 (3.8%)	1 (1%)
Total	300	9	5

The children and parents responded almost equally. Most of the respondents stated that gloves are worn to protect the doctor and the patient (94.9% and 96.2%, respectively) (Table 2).

TABLE 2: CHILDREN'S AND PARENT'S RESPONSE ON WHETHER GLOVES ARE WORN TO PROTECT DENTIST OR PATIENTS

	Dentist only No (%)	Patient only No (%)	Both No (%)
Children	4 (2.5%)	4 (2.5%)	149 (94.9%)
Parents	2 (1.3%)	4 (2.5%)	151 (96.2%)
Total	6	7	300

90.4% of children and 87.3% of parents did not like going to the dentist who did not wear gloves (Table 3).

TABLE 3: CHILDREN'S AND PARENT'S RESPONSE ON WHETHER THEY WOULD ATTEND A DENTIST WHO DON'T WEAR GLOVES

	Yes No (%)	No No (%)
Children	15 (9.6%)	142 (90.4%)
Parents	20 (12.7%)	137 (87.3%)
Total	35	279

The majority of children (92.4%) and parents (94.9%) believed that each patient's gloves should be changed after dental treatment (Table 4) with no significant difference in response between the two groups.

TABLE 4: CHILDREN'S AND PARENT'S RESPONSE ON WHETHER DENTIST SHOULD CHANGE GLOVES OR WASHING IS SUFFICIENT

	Change gloves No (%)	Washing sufficient No (%)	Decision by dentist No (%)
Children	145 (92.4%)	5 (3%)	7 (4.5%)
Parents	149 (94.9%)	1 (1%)	7 (4.5%)
Total	294	6	14

DISCUSSION:

This study compared children's responses to questions about the use of gloves by dentists. According to Piaget, at the age of eleven, the thought process of children resembles that of an adult and is able to understand the concepts of health, disease and prevention. Most children develop the ability to deal with abstract concepts and abstract reasoning by age eleven. Most children and their parents felt that the dentist should routinely wear gloves during dental treatment. This result is in line with most previous studies. A high percentage of study participants considered the gloves worn by the dentist during treatment to be an important aspect of cross-infection control, indicating a high level of public awareness of the issue. There was no significant difference in the reactions between the children and their parents. This result showed that children today are very much aware of the diseases that are spreading today, and their thinking is almost similar to that of adults. In Pakistan 81.8% of general dentists wear gloves during dental treatment, while 100% of the dental staff at a university facility reported routine wearing gloves while treating patients.

In dentistry, gloves are worn to protect the dentist and patients from infection and to prevent disease transmission from patient to patient. In this study, the overwhelming majority of children and their parents believe that gloves are worn to protect both the dentist and the patient. This result contrasts with the earlier finding of Bowen *et al*, when 31% of patients believed that the main reason for wearing gloves was to protect the dentist from the patient and 19% of patients surveyed considered that the main reason for wearing

gloves was to protect the patient from the dentist. But this statement is in line with previous reports.

Most of the children and their parents mentioned that they would not go to the dentist who did not wear gloves during treatment (90.4%, 87.3% respectively). This is more than the results obtained in previous studies. A small percentage of children and parents (9.65, 12.7%, respectively) would report to the dentist without gloves. These figures were significantly lower than the 51.51 and 34% of patients in previous reports by Burke *et al*. And Otuyemi *et al*, respectively. However, these results contradict the fact that 2.1% of children and 3.8% of parents considered wearing gloves is unnecessary. Increased awareness of cross infection among parents and children could explain these results, with no significant difference between the two groups.

Most of the participants argued for the need for dentists to wear gloves and for the replacement of gloves between patients. This reflects a greater awareness of both groups of the importance of infection control. The current findings are higher than those reported by others, which may be due to the impact of media reports on infectious diseases such as AIDS on humans and made them more aware of the importance of infection control procedures in dental practice. This awareness is almost similar in both children and their parents, with no significant difference between them.

CONCLUSION:

Most of the participants in this study indicated that dentists should wear gloves when treating their

patients and that they should not take their children to a dentist who does not have adequate infection control procedures. The study did not show any significant difference in the responses of children and their parents to the above-mentioned questions about their attitude to the use of gloves by dentists.

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